

RETHINKING NEGOTIATION-FEMINISM IN RAZINAT T. MOHAMMED'S *THE TRAVAILS OF A FIRST WIFE*

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Abstract:

Nego-feminism, like other African feminist frameworks, is celebrated for being a suitable model for the African context of gender relations which favor negotiation, relationality, and complementarity against outright confrontation and rebellion. However, scholars have argued that negotiation has limitations which, oftentimes, sustain patriarchy and promote complicity. This study therefore interrogates the limitations of negotiation in Razinat T. Mohammed's *The Travails of a First Wife*. It argues that negotiation in some contexts like unyielding patriarchy can become a burden rather than a liberating tool for women. Nego-feminism is adopted as a theoretical model of analysis to explore how negotiation is employed as a feminist strategy in a novel set in a deeply patriarchal society like Northern Nigeria. The analysis reveals the pros and cons of the protagonist's negotiation with her husband and other male characters in the novel and the cost to her rights and general wellbeing.

Keywords: African feminism, Nego-feminism, Negotiation, African Women's Fiction

Introduction

The emergence of feminist thought in Africa has been credited to the incompatibility of Western feminism with African values. African feminist scholars have argued that various factors such as kinship structures and communal

values contribute to gender discourse on the continent (Bakare-Yusuf, 2003; Oyewumi, 1997). As a result, different frameworks have emerged which are said to align with the realities of African women. One of such frameworks is Nego-feminism, a concept developed by Nnaemeka Obioma to describe a strand of feminism of “negotiation, give and take, compromise, and balance” (Nnaemeka, 2003, p. 378). The framework privileges negotiation and compromise over outright confrontation.

Despite the growing adoption of nego-feminism in literary analysis, gaps persist in understanding and establishing the limitations of negotiation for gender equity. Most of the existing studies focused on the strengths of negotiation and how it is an important survival tool for women in patriarchal societies. For instance, Muhammad et. al. (2017) employed nego-feminism in their exploration of Zaynab Alkali's *The Stillborn* and *Virtuous Woman*, concluding that negotiation is an important tool in reducing or eradicating gender war. Abdulkarim (2020) also adopted Nego-feminism in her analysis of Lola Shoneyin's *The Secret Life of Baba Segi's Wives*. The study encouraged the employment of negotiation in daily lives, concluding that harmony and national development can be achieved through negotiation and dialogue. Also, Abdulkarim and Alkali (2024) employed the model in the analysis of Ba'aram Alkali's *Personal Angle*. The study also finds that negotiation in marital life eradicates gender supremacy tussle. Muhammad et al. (2016) adopted this model in their engagement with Abubakar Gimba's *Sacred Apples*.

The study which explores the use of negotiation in the novel concludes that negotiation in man-woman relationship gives room for commitment and trust between them. Nego-feminism was also adopted by Zebenay and Yazbec (2025) in their examination of women empowerment in Flora Nwapa's *Efuru*. The study revealed how female characters employ various strategies like cooperation, negotiation and compromise to empower themselves. Ilo (2025) adopted three African models, including Nego-feminism in his exploration of Nigerian Nollywood movies. The study which focuses on the intersection of feminist film theory and the politics of gender representation asserts that Nego-feminism does not seek for gender roles to be reversed or promote outright rebellion against patriarchy but encourages women to find power within traditional structures. As

much as these studies highlight the possible advantages of negotiation, they do not account for the limitations which place the female gender at a disadvantage.

This study, therefore, seeks to interrogate the limitations of negotiation in Razinat T. Mohammed's *The Travails of a First Wife* through a qualitative methodology in the analysis of the text. Nnaemeka Obioma's Nego-feminism is adopted as theoretical anchor to investigate the limitations of negotiation as portrayed in the text. Relevant literatures on Nego-feminism are also reviewed to support the analysis.

Contextualizing Nego-Feminism

Nnaemeka Obioma in her 2003 journal article “Nego-feminism: Theorizing, Practicing, and Pruning Africa’s way”, proposed Nego-feminism as a strand of African feminism which privileges negotiation and compromise over outright confrontation. Nnaemeka argues that African women often survive patriarchy through strategies that apply cultural wisdom. She described Nego-feminism as “feminism of negotiation. No-ego feminism” (p. 377) which suggests that African women navigate patriarchal structures through negotiation rather than outright rebellion:

It knows when, where, and how to detonate patriarchal land mines; it also knows when, where, and how to go around patriarchal land mines. In other words, it knows when, where, and how to negotiate with or negotiate around patriarchy in different contexts. For African women, feminism is an act that evokes the dynamism and shifts of a process as opposed to the stability and reification of a construct, a framework (p. 378).

The theory is reliant upon the idea that gender relations in Africa are tied to cultural and communal values. As Nnaemeka posits, negotiation is not to be seen as a sign of weakness. Rather, it should be seen as a tool that allows women navigate patriarchal structures without disrupting communal setting. In addition, the model identifies that women “know when, where, and how to negotiate with or negotiate around patriarchy” (p. 378). This application of timing and cultural intelligence determines how African women claim their space and solidify their position in the society. Nkealah (2016) in advancing the model, categorises Nego-feminism as a strand of African feminist thought originating from the continent to

reflect local realities. She observes that the model, like other African feminist frameworks such as Snail Sense feminism, advocates compromise and collaboration to achieve gender balance.

A number of literary scholars have adopted Nego-feminism in their analysis of African women's writings as literary texts reflect the everyday strategies employed by African women. Their studies show how negotiation is deployed by women in various circumstances. Abdulkarim's (2020, p. 159) exploration of Shoneyin's *The Secret Lives of Baba Segi's Wives*, for instance, observes that women in polygamous homes maintain peace and secure their homes through negotiations. She notes that "nego-feminism is used as a strategy by the women to negotiate their way with men in order to build a harmonious society." Alkali (2013) offers quite the comprehensive study on Nego-feminism in his investigation of six Nigerian novels where he observes that outright confrontation may bring about backlash in African patriarchal setting. He concludes that women of African descent often employ negotiation to navigate cultural expectations. Also, Muhammad et al. (2017) contribute to this discussion, arguing that negotiation helps women to create a balance between societal expectations of female obedience and their desire for independence. This resonates with the focus of Nego-feminism on societal stability.

Nego-feminism has also been applied beyond literary studies. Browne et al. (2024) deployed it in their analysis of reproductive health politics where the study argues that alliances can be built in making decisions on abortion, especially in conservative societies through the employment of negotiation-based strategies. Udenigwe et al. (2023) also employed the model in their study of the socio-cultural realities of pregnant women in Nigeria. The study finds that "women negotiate authority by ascribing the role of decision maker to their men spouses while maintaining influence over their pregnancy healthcare decisions and actions" (p. 1).

However, Nego-feminism has come under criticism despite its growing recognition. Scholars have argued that the framework is not without flaws and can be ineffective in some contexts. Okafor-Maduka (2025) raises a strong concern over negotiation-based theories like Nego-feminism and Snail-sense feminism. She argues that negotiation may be ineffective in cases of severe abuse. "Snail-

sense and Nego-feminism are double-edged. While they provide strategies for navigating oppressive systems, they may also discourage urgency (p. 4),” adding that the model has to advocate not only for negotiation but for protective exit strategies that prioritize women's safety, well-being and freedom (p. 3).” This speaks to the limitations of negotiation as such approach may not be suitable in the context of domestic violence.

Oloruntoba (2019) equally questions the idea of negotiation which to him, leans more towards managing patriarchal structures rather than dismantling them completely to allow for gender balance. He queries:

The problem with this ideology is the *a priori* position in which women naturally find themselves. Why do they find themselves walking amidst landmines? Why do men have to be landmines? Nego-feminism seem to be managing patriarchy rather than tackling it. The questions that follow this are, for how long would they continue to negotiate and manage the problem? At what point would they tackle the entity responsible for setting up the metaphorical explosive? The questions above suggest that nego-feminism seem to create more questions than answers (p. 37).

This aligns with the position of Onabolu (2019) that “the approach of negotiation panders to male hegemony and fails to dismantle a heavily patriarchal society”. This suggests that theories like Nego-feminism may result in consequences like reinforcing oppressive systems to sustain harmony. Indeed, works that have deployed the model identify that it places the burden of sustaining harmony on the female gender. In the novels analyzed by Alkali (2013), the women endure maltreatment and adjust to unfair cultural and societal expectations to keep their homes. Abdulkarim (2020) also reveals that women in polygamous homes negotiate their positions to the benefit of the man.

Rethinking Nego-feminism in *The Travails of a First Wife*

Nnaemeka's Nego-feminism rests upon the notion that African women have always successfully navigated patriarchy through negotiations and compromise. Although this feminist approach mirrors the reality of many African women, it fails to establish when negotiation and compromise should end for sustainable gender equity to be established. It equally vests the responsibility of negotiating

and compromising on the female gender. This imposes the responsibility of societal balance only on the female without any particular role expected from males.

Razinat Talatu Mohammed's *The Travails of a First Wife* provides a suitable literary avenue to explore this. The novel chronicles the life of Zarah, a first wife in a polygynous home and how she navigates the challenges she encounters in her marriage which affects her general wellbeing. Key characters include the protagonist, Zarah; her husband, Ibrahim; his two other wives, Kellu and Fantere; and Ibrahim and Zarah's illegitimate child, Babagana. Through the lived experiences of Zarah in her matrimonial home, the novel reflects that negotiation can become a heavy burden on the woman, especially in places where patriarchy is rigid and manipulative.

At the core of Nego-feminism is the assumption that patriarchal structures can be flexible which gives room for women to negotiate. However, the patriarchal structure presented in *The Travails of a First Wife* is rigid and unyielding, making negotiation ineffective. Throughout the novel, Zarah's husband, Ibrahim represents a partner that is not open to dialogue. His decision to marry not just one but two additional wives is made without consultation and consideration for his wife's emotion. In announcing his decision, Ibrahim informs Zarah that he has "come to rub pepper as it were, to your wounds at this time of the night" (p. 56), adding that "in four days' time, I will be getting married not to one woman but two women" (p. 56). Although his culture and religion permit him, the manner by which it is executed is without regard for how his wife may take it, considering that he has a long history of emotional irresponsibility towards her. Ibrahim's behavior gives no room for negotiation as he never intends to negotiate in the first place. This reveals a major limitation as negotiation only works when all the parties involved are willing. Ibrahim in this case occupies a position where his authority is unquestionable. This makes negotiation impossible for Zarah.

The society within which the novel is set is a deeply patrilineal one which gives men superior and unquestionable powers over the women. The men enjoy both social and religious support. They rather enjoy their patriarchal leverage than give room for any negotiation. While polygyny is normalized within the society by culture and religion, the emotional harm it causes women is not addressed. This is

why Ibrahim questions why his women are finding it difficult to accept. “What was he doing wrong? He wondered. Was it not his prerogative right to marry as many as four women? Why would the women not understand that he was doing nothing wrong? (p. 50). Kellu's aunt, Hajja Dana, while consoling her upon receiving the news of Ibrahim's plan to marry an additional wife confirms that “men are wont to do such things without knowing what the women feel” (p. 46). This shows how men's desires are prioritized over the well-being of the women, making negotiation difficult to achieve.

The consequence of accepting polygyny without enforcing its rightful practice as stipulated by both culture and religion is the unhealthy competition that occurs amongst co-wives. Brides are taught right from their homes to see polygynous homes as a battleground where they must do all it takes to survive. Kellu is warned by elderly women in her family regarding her co-wives to “keep to your side of the house as much as you can. Do not attempt to be too close to anyone of them because you have to understand that a co-wife can never be your friend however she claims to love you” (p. 83). Instead of addressing the wrong practice of polygyny, families also resort to spiritual fortifications to solidify their daughters' status in polygynous homes. Mohammed notes that when Zarah was getting married:

She was scared because the age was that of sorcerers who paraded themselves as co-wives. She thought of the charms her own family had given her for self-protection. They were three rag knots thrown under her bed and one she was to wear round her neck at night, each time she was not sleeping in her husband's room. Well, that was from her end. Women she had heard could become diabolic as to want to cause harm to the other woman in that sort of situation in order to be the object of attention of the man and gain his favours (p. 81).

The patriarchal society also conditions women to see marriage as the ultimate goal, lack of which a woman is seen as incomplete. This makes wives like Zarah tie their success to their ability to preserve their marriage regardless of their suffering. Men like Ibrahim weaponize this societal design, making him to threaten divorce at different occasions just to win arguments. When Ibrahim

pronounces divorce on Zarah for refusing to sell her house on his instruction, the author notes that:

Her [Zarah] fear was more about the shame she was going to face if she lost out on her marriage. The feeling sent painful shivers through her spine. She was scared because the society was a conservative one that still did not recognize a woman if she was not appended to a man, as wife. In her head, she had plans to establish herself as an estate owner, starting with the house in Damaturu but she could not even begin just then, she needed the protection that only marriage could provide and when she was more grounded and confident, she would think of something for her old age (p. 220).

This may have informed Zarah's decision to remain in the marriage at the expense of her own happiness. Contrary to the nego-feminist stance that negotiation helps women navigate patriarchal structures, the novel depicts how the approach can sometimes embolden the same structure it is designed to negotiate. Zarah's continuous indulgence of Ibrahim represents nego-feminism expectations of patience and compromise. Although her employment of these virtues is strategic as they help keep her matrimony which she so much desires to, Ibrahim does not compromise in commensurate measure, making him a non-contributor. Ibrahim has always presented Zarah with difficult choices to choose from to his own benefit. An instance is when their son, Babagana, visits to spend the holiday with the family, Ibrahim refuses due to his fear that his other wives will suspect the paternity of the boy as he [Babagana] continues to grow to resemble him. Another instance is Ibrahim asking Zarah to choose between their marriage and her house in Damaturu. Zarah refuses, insisting that it is the only inheritance she will leave for her son since his illegitimate birth has stripped him of his entitlement to Ibrahim's estate. It takes the intervention of Zarah's guardian to get Ibrahim to withdraw the divorce he earlier pronounced, assuring that Zarah will not visit the house anymore as long as she remains Ibrahim's wife. This persistent compromise to the benefit of Ibrahim sustains his rigid and manipulative nature.

Zarah's agreeable nature emboldens Ibrahim to treat her badly. Even when she exercises silence, Ibrahim still finds a way to claim the victim. Mohammed notes that "Ibrahim had always treated her with disdain and whenever she seemed to be

having an upper hand, he would suddenly overturn the table so that she was always on the defensive while he would slide off unscathed” (p. 52). This is evident where Zarah maintains silence while Ibrahim is announcing his decision to marry additional two wives:

“Will you just sit there and say nothing? Am I not talking to you? His voice was authoritarian as he attempted to slide into his usual tact of overturning the table on her. She was certain about one thing and that was not to say anything to him. So, I have become so useless in your eyes that you now turn me into a madman that talks to himself? Still silence. Zarah, you defy me? When she did not respond even to the threat in his voice, he stormed out of the room, banging the door with a loud clatter (p. 57).

This points to how manipulation is employed within negotiation. Another instance of Ibrahim's manipulative behavior is when Zarah refuses to yield to his demand to sell her house. Ibrahim responds that she has “changed from the woman I knew. When you begin to talk about a house that belongs to you alone then I become afraid of what else you will come up with” (p. 197). One of the ideas behind nego-feminism is to achieve harmony in the home and the society by extension. However, what is not much talked about is that the burden of harmony may be rested upon the compromise and sacrifice of one party to the advantage of the other. Such imbalance is presented in the text where the protagonist, Zarah, is burdened by the responsibility of constantly keeping the peace at home. A burden that should have been shared amongst all parties involved in order to complement the effort of one another. Throughout the text, Zarah is the one making compromises. This involves ceding her rights and enduring the injustice thrown at her. This is vividly captured one night when:

Zarah sat in her room thinking and wondering at the sort of happenings going on around the house. She knew that Ibrahim would have known that she was to be in his room but she did not also expect that he was going to send Kellu away when she walked into his room in her characteristic manner of over dousing herself in perfumery. She reassured herself that sometimes, it was better to remain foolish and at times, forgo your rights to attain the peace of mind that the body needed. She remembered the saying

that at the bottom of patience, one finds heaven. She very much hoped to find that heaven in due course (p. 191).

This is the kind of cope mechanism Zarah resorts to in order for peace to reign. Although this allows her to keep her marriage, the long-term effect is the emotional and psychological cost of one-sided negotiation which she continues to pay. The author presents Zarah's marital life as one full of loneliness and emotional struggle. She negotiates for the love and respect of the husband she has sacrificed a lot for. This requires her to silence herself, remain calm even in pain and in most cases avoid expressing anger and suppress her emotional needs to maintain peace. Mohammed narrates a scenario where:

hot tears blurred her vision and she was almost running into the rear of a silver-coloured Mercedes car in front of her. It was the sudden slam on the brakes of her car that helped her regain composure. She felt like running out of the car and screaming in her loudest voice if only it could relieve her of the fire that was building itself inside her chest. Her thoughts suddenly went to Ibrahim's so-called joke of asking her if the tears she had wept since knowing him could not fill a drum. The day he had mentioned that mundane joke, she had evaluated her relationship with him and knew that it was 90% pains. It was not even a 50/50 kind of thing but in spite of all, she could not explain why she could not consider some other men but always had to be him. Her family and friends had wondered why it had to be him all the time, even when he showed signs of unfaithfulness it had always been to him that she ran (p. 28).

This shows how excessive negotiation can take a psychological toll on women especially when not reciprocated. Zarah's emotional burden reveals how expensive negotiation is as it requires a great deal of emotional battle from women. Nego-feminism may have assumed that the ability to negotiate is equal amongst women. However, some women have more leverage than the others. This makes the outcome of negotiation vary from woman to woman. While some women have strong bargaining power, possibly due to some considerations they enjoy, the lack of such considerations can place other women at disadvantage. Bringing this into perspective, Zarah's co-wives enjoy some kind of leverage she [Zarah] does not possess. She is described as:

someone most people would not consider beautiful because of the protrusion of her mouth, which gave the face an extra elongation at the chin, and a large nose better suited on the face of a huge man. She had a large scar on the upper right side of her face which gave the face an aquiline appearance resembling the outer most cover of the gills of a fish. In spite of her large eyes, which if they could stand alone, could be said to be beautiful but in spite of the pair, she was a plain woman (p. 2).

This description speaks to how people in the community see her relationship with Ibrahim since inception. They always “wondered what it was that kept him attached to the girl when it was clear that she was not remotely his kind of woman if he had the choice. Being as handsome as he was, girls fought to get his attention and yet, it was always to that ugly Zarah that he went back. Everyone believed that she had bewitched him with some evil spells that kept him perpetually at her mercy (p. 66). Another contributory factor that diminishes Zarah's bargaining power is her inability to conceive a legitimate child for Ibrahim, having birth one, Babangana out of wedlock, a child which the society conditions her to choose between him and her husband. This societal conditioning prevents him and Ibrahim from claiming ownership of the 17 years old boy, making Zarah negotiate for Ibrahim to marry her instead of laying claim to the boy. Added to this is that Zarah has committed series of abortion for Ibrahim in order to conceal their unlawful intimacy which the society frowns at. This is revealed when Zarah expresses her displeasure about how she is being treated by Ibrahim. She declares to Ibrahim that:

You have not been fair to me". She said in a raised voice. "How can you have no pity whatsoever in your heart for me? Since my childhood, you have made me terminate one pregnancy after another and now when you have condemned me to a fate of bareness you marry not one but two women at a go and now the only thing that I have left in the world you want to keep away from me. How can you be so heartless? This boy is your own flesh and blood and yet you throw him away because your women are pregnant?" (p. 130).

However, the ability of the other wives to conceive make them enjoy preferential treatment in the hands of their husband, an injustice that is committed to the

knowledge of Zarah. “I have been watching you give preferential treatments your wives as though I was a mere servant to all of you. I blame you for the daily disrespect that those women, especially Fantere dishes out to me” (p. 153).

Conclusion

This study has explored the limitations of nego-feminism using Razinat T. Mohammed’s *The Travails of a First Wife* as case study. The analysis reveals that the protagonist's persistent negotiation although makes her preserve her marriage, it comes at a cost which implicates on her rights and general well-being. *The Travails of a First Wife* offers a reflection on the limitations of negotiation. While nego-feminism acknowledges that women assert agency within a patriarchal society, the text depicts that negotiation may serve no purpose in situations where patriarchy remains unyielding as a result of societal support and where a woman's silence is exploited as obedience. This also includes situations where women lack bargaining power.

Zarah's lived experiences with an unyielding husband in a strictly patriarchal setting exposes the cost of excessive negotiation. It reveals that one-sided negotiation can be an oppressive rather than a liberating tool. The novel reflects that although negotiation can sustain any relationship, it may not be effective in dismantling unjust practices. It tells that real change may require more than just negotiation. It requires both cultural and institutional reforms, including a fresh look at male-female relationship where the well-being of women does not take the back seat.

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